

NEW COMPOUNDS OF GALLIUM. PART III. PREPARATION AND RESOLUTION OF COMPLEX OXALATO COMPOUNDS OF GALLIUM INTO OPTICAL ISOMERS.

BY PANCEANAN NEOGI AND NIHAR KUMAR DUTT.

The paper describes the preparation and properties of the complex oxalates of gallium with oxalates of sodium, potassium, ammonium and strychnine and also the resolution of the potassium and ammonium salts into their optical isomers by means of the strychnine; preparation of their *d*-components has been described.

Existing literature shows that the complex salts of gallium have not yet been obtained, though double salts, like alums, are well known. As various complex oxalates of trivalent metals like aluminium, chromium and cobalt have been prepared and successfully resolved, it has been our aim to prepare the corresponding compounds of gallium and if possible to resolve them. We have now been able to prepare the sodium, potassium, and ammonium complex oxalates of gallium and have actually resolved the potassium and ammonium salts into their *dextro*-rotatory components by means of strychnine.

The successful resolution of these gallium salts shows that they are complex hexa-co-ordinated compounds with a spatial distribution of the chelate groups round the central gallium atom, and the octahedral structures of the optically active isomers are to be represented as follows :

Wahl (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 399) was able to prepare the *d*-variety of only the ammonium salt of the corresponding complex aluminium salt, but we have prepared the *d*-varieties of both the ammonium and potassium salt of the corresponding gallium-oxalato-acid. The first optically active salts of gallium have been obtained by Neogi and Nandi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 399) but this is the first time that a racemic gallium salt has been resolved into optical modification.

The racemic sodium, potassium and ammonium salts were obtained by digesting freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide with the corresponding acid oxalates and their general formula is represented by $M_3 [Ga (C_2O_4)_3] \cdot 3H_2O$, which is analogous to the corresponding aluminium salts. The strychnine salt was prepared by the action of strychnine nitrate on the ammonium salt which is the most soluble of the three when it was obtained as a crystalline precipitate having the formula $[Ga (C_2O_4)_3] (H^+C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)_3 \cdot 12H_2O$, also analogous to the corresponding aluminium salt.

The strychnine salt is *laevo*-rotatory with $[M]_D^{25} = -241^\circ$ and consists of *l*-strychnine-*d*-gallium oxalate and *l*-strychnine-*l*-gallium-oxalate. An attempt to separate them by fractional crystallisation from the solution in warm water was unsuccessful as the salt racemises quickly in it. They were however, separated by repeated fractional extraction with cold water when owing to differences in solubility of the two isomers in it, the *d*-variety, which was more insoluble, was obtained in the residue, the *l*-component passing in the solution.

It was found that after six fractional extractions of the original substance, the molecular rotation of -241° was changed to $+140^\circ$, which figure remained stationary. The *l*-strychnine-*d*-gallium oxalate was thus obtained.

Having separated the *d*-variety of the strychnine salt, the *d*-potassium and ammonium salts were obtained by the double decomposition with potassium and ammonium iodides respectively.

The gallium was estimated, after decomposing the complex salt with strong sulphuric acid and precipitating it as hydroxide and then ignited and weighed as oxide. The sodium and potassium were estimated in the filtrates as sulphates after evaporation to dryness. The gallium in the strychnine salt was determined by igniting it until white gallium oxide was obtained. The nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Alkali Salts of Gallium Tri-oxalato Acid, $M_3 [Ga(C_2O_4)_3] \cdot 3H_2O$.

Ammonium Salt.—Equimolecular quantities of ammonium oxalate and oxalic acid were dissolved in water and boiled. The hot solution was then slowly poured over freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide, suspended in water until the major portion of the hydroxide was dissolved leaving behind a small portion of the undissolved hydroxide. This is essentially necessary to ensure the purity of the complex ammonium salt. The hot solution was filtered, concentrated on the water-bath and then allowed to crystallise

in a desiccator when the salt was obtained in beautiful crystals. The salt is very easily soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol. The substance is stable in the solid state as well as in solution. {Found : N, 9'5, 9'48 ; Ga, 15'2, 15'1. $(\text{NH}_4)_3[\text{Ga}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 9'5 ; Ga, 15'8 per cent}.

Potassium salt was obtained very similarly to the ammonium salt substituting ammonium oxalate with potassium oxalate. It resembles the ammonium salt in solubility and other properties though the ammonium salt is more soluble in water. {Found : Ga, 13'9, 13'8 ; K, 23'2, 23'1. $\text{K}_3[\text{Ga}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ga, 13'8 ; K, 23'2 per cent}.

Sodium salt was obtained as above using sodium oxalate in the place of ammonium oxalate. In solubility and other properties it resembles the potassium salt. {Found : Ga, 15'2, 15'2 ; Na, 15'01, 15'2. $\text{Na}_3[\text{Ga}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ga, 15'2 ; Na, 15'0 per cent}.

l-Strychnine Gallium Trioxalate, $l\text{-}[\text{Ga}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] (\text{HC}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$.—The strychnine salt was obtained by precipitating a cold saturated solution of strychnine nitrate with a cold saturated solution of the ammonium salt of gallium trioxalato-acid. The precipitate was filtered, washed and dried. The salt is slightly soluble in cold water, easily soluble in warm water and in alcohol. In 1% solution of the salt in aqueous alcohol (1 : 1) in a 2 dm. tube, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -15'5^\circ$ $[M]_D^{25} = -242^\circ$. {Found : N, 5'5, 5'47 ; Ga, 4'0, 4'6. $[\text{Ga}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] (\text{H}'\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires 4'5 ; 5'4 per cent}.

Preparation of l-Strychnine-d-gallium Oxalate from l-Strychnine-gallium Oxalate.

The process of fractional extraction was employed as was done by Wahl (*loc. cit.*) in the case of the corresponding aluminium salt. For extraction 20 g. of the powdered salt were shaken with cold distilled water, filtered and the residue dried between filter papers and finally on a porous tile.

The results of an extraction are given below and 1% solution in (1 : 1) alcohol was examined in the polarimeter in a 2 dm. tube.

		$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	$[M]_D^{25}$.
	Original substance	-15'5°	-241'1°
1.	Residue after extraction with 100 c.c. of H_2O	- 15°	-233'2°
2.	„ „ 300	- 9'5°	-147'7°
3.	„ „ 106	- 8'5°	-132'2°

		$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	$[M]_D^{25}$.
4.	Residue after extraction with 200 c.c. H ₂ O	- 6°	-93'3"
5.	" "	-4'5"	-72'6"
6.	" "	+ 9°	+ 140°
7.	" "	+ 9°	+ 140°

The specific rotation of the *l*-strychnine-*d*-gallium oxalate was therefore +29° and $[M]_D^{25} = +140^\circ$.

Preparation of d-Potassium and d-Ammonium Gallium Oxalate.

Dextro-varieties of the potassium and ammonium salts were obtained by the double decomposition of the strychnine salt with the solutions of the corresponding iodides. Half the quantity of the *d*-strychnine salt was treated with KI and the other half with NH₄I. A weighed quantity of the strychnine salt was taken in a mortar and the theoretical quantity of KI was dissolved in water and added to it and triturated. Strychnine iodide was precipitated and the solution tested for any excess of KI. The solution was then filtered and to the filtrate was added a large excess of alcohol and cooled. The salt was precipitated, filtered, and immediately dried under an electric fan.

Similarly, the ammonium salt was obtained by using ammonium iodide.

Salt.	Gallium		$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	$[M]_D^{25}$.
	Found.	Req.		
I <i>d</i> -K ₃ [Ga (C ₂ O ₄) ₃], 3H ₂ O	13.6	13.8	+ 16.5°	+ 83.3°
II <i>d</i> -(NH ₄) ₃ [Ga (C ₂ O ₄) ₃], 3H ₂ O	15.2	15.8	+ 15.5°	+ 68.5°

Racemisation of the Active Potassium and Ammonium Salts.

These active salts of potassium and ammonium gradually became racemic in a short time. The following table will show the rate of racemisation.

<i>d</i> -K.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	$[M]_D^{25}$.
Original reading	+ 16.5°	+ 83.3°
Reading after 3 hours	+ 14°	+ 67.5°
27 "	+ 4°	+ 20.1°
<i>d</i> -NH ₄ .		
Original reading	+ 15.5°	+ 68.5°
Reading after 3 hours	+ 12.5°	+ 55.3°
27 "	+ 3°	+ 13.3°